

STUDY OF THE SPECIFIC ACTIVITY OF A BIOACTIVE SUPPLEMENT FOR THE PREVENTION OF CONSTIPATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17342170>

Relevance: According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and other medical research data, 10–20% of the global population suffers from chronic constipation. This issue is especially prevalent among women, the elderly, pregnant women, and individuals with sedentary lifestyles. Constipation not only causes discomfort but can also lead to hemorrhoids, anal fissures, intestinal dysfunction, and chronic toxicosis. Long-term use of many synthetic laxatives can result in intestinal habituation (tolerance), dysbiosis, and disruption of the water-electrolyte balance. Therefore, there is a growing demand for natural, safe, and effective alternatives. The global laxative market exceeded \$10 billion USD in 2024, and continues to grow annually. In the bioactive supplements segment, constipation-relief products stand out as a distinct and growing category.

Objective of the Study: To investigate the specific activity of a powdered blend composed of natural bioactive substances aimed at preventing constipation and improving metabolism in the human body.

Methods and Materials: The anti-constipation effects of bioactive powders No. 1, 2, 3, and 4 were studied using 24 white rats weighing 190–210 grams. The test animals were divided into five groups of six rats each.

Composition of the powders: Bioactive Powder No. 1: Garcinia Cambogia –30g, Brazilian Coffee – 20 g, L-Carnitine – 10 g, Senna – 10 g, Green Coffee – 10 g, Bioactive Powder No. 2: Garcinia Cambogia – 20 g, Brazilian Coffee – 30 g, L-Carnitine – 10 g, Senna – 5 g, Green Coffee – 15 g, Bioactive Powder No. 3: Garcinia Cambogia – 30 g, Brazilian Coffee – 20 g, L-Carnitine – 15 g, Senna – 5 g, Green Coffee – 10 g, Bioactive Powder No. 4: Garcinia Cambogia – 20 g, Brazilian Coffee – 30 g, L-Carnitine – 10 g, Senna – 15 g, Green Coffee – 5 g

The study assessed the increase in fecal mass as a measure of laxative effect at 50 mg/kg and 25 mg/kg doses.

Results: In animals treated with Bioactive Powder No. 1, the fecal mass increased by 1.73 times at a 50 mg/kg dose and 1.5 times at a 25 mg/kg dose compared to the control group. For Powder No. 2, fecal mass increased 1.45 times at 50 mg/kg and 1.4 times at 25 mg/kg. For Powder No. 3, the increases were 1.4 times at 50 mg/kg and 1.34 times at 25 mg/kg. Powder No. 4 showed the lowest effect: 1.2 times at 50 mg/kg and 1.1 times at 25 mg/kg.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the specific activity of bioactive powders No. 1, 2, 3, and 4 against constipation was studied. It was found that Bioactive Powder No. 1 demonstrated the highest anti-constipation activity. Therefore, continued use of Bioactive Powder No. 1 as a remedy for constipation is recommended.